

SPECIFICS OF BORROWED WORDS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Abstract: The goal of the current article is to examine the linguocultural aspects of terms that have been assimilated from English into Uzbek. These words are often employed in daily speech and contribute to the transmission of national stereotypes and value systems from one generation to the next. The purpose of the research is to examine the relationship between language and culture, as well as the issues that arise when they are combined, as well as how each has an impact on the other's growth and how they relate to social life, and philosophy, psychology

Keywords: linguoculturology, cultureme, language and culture, culture layers, interrelation, cultural features, borrowed words, loan words, word group.

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It should be emphasized that there are no pure languages in existence. The existence of a language just through its own words does not determine its purity. One of the most significant linguistic processes is the blending of languages and their interaction. It is evident that the language's conceptual perspective is similarly broadened by the use of new terms. In addition, language acquisition is common and allows for cultural immersion. The cultureme serves as the language's fundamental structural unit at the linguocultural level, and many linguists have proposed a way for analyzing borrowed terms based on this model. Every country has its own culture, traditions, and, obviously, culturemes that reflect various aspects of that culture in the language of that country. These culturemes offer unique semantic and linguocultural characteristics of borrowings. Every individual is a part of the national culture, which consists of national customs, languages, histories, and literature. Studies on cross-cultural communication, language and culture relationships, and language identity are crucial nowadays. One of the main focuses of linguistic research, it covers a variety of topics related to a nation's cultural diversity and linguistic spirit, as well as ideas of conversational structure. This scientific field investigates how a language captures a nation's character. It includes national-cultural knowledge through voice communication and is related to other fields of study including philosophy, logics, sociology, anthropology, and semantics. The evolution of linguistic and philosophical theories in the 19th and 20th centuries had a significant impact on the emergence of linguocultural research. A linguocultureme is a linguistic or speech unit that defines one aspect of a culture,

as stated in U.K. Yusupov's book "Contrastive linguistics of the English and Uzbek languages." As a result, linguoculturology is a subfield of linguistics that studies how language and culture interact and how to convey culture through language [5, p. 262]. However, it is made clear that linguoculture studies how a person's spiritual condition is reflected in their language in their social environment. Each subject, or subset thereof, has a study tool that belongs to it. It is acknowledged that the term "cultureme" (or "linguocultureme") is employed in scientific research to name the subject of linguoculturology. The distinction between a cultureme and a lexeme may be seen in the definition of a cultureme: a cultureme is a word, phrase, or even a whole sentence in a language that encompasses unique national, social, or mental characteristics that are particular to the a language's culture. In accordance with the many cultural layers, several scholars have effectively distinguished subtypes of one language:

1) Literary language is associated with the elite culture; 2) Popular language is associated with "the third culture;" 3) Dialects and sayings are associated with the popular culture; and 4) Argot (words and expressions used by select individuals but difficult for others to understand) is associated with the traditional professional culture. The fact that cultural linguistics is intended to represent all of this diversity in cultural values and the ways in which they are expressed in various linguistic levels across various languages is another factor to take into account. A borrowed term, or a word having a specific lexical meaning distinct from the original word's meaning, appearing in a text is referred to as being necessary for communication. One of the best instances of how languages and cultures interact, resulting in the development of universal ideals and languages, is borrowing. Unlike lending, which involves gaining a new word from another language, borrowing entails adopting a new word's name as well as its meaning from the original language. In fact, it is obvious that the first manner that adopting words aids in the development of the internal lexicons of the languages. There was no such language, no such words. However, there are other languages, primarily those used in research and public-political terminology, that have played and continue to play a larger role in the dissemination of ideas. Greek and Latin performed this role in European history, but subsequently German and French. Additionally, they outlined the four main causes of lexical borrowings in various languages around the world. They have something in common with appropriating fresh ideas or concepts while employing duplicates of already existing terminology. Around 15% of the most recent English words, according to M.A. Breiter, are borrowed since they don't have a name in the target language. The Russian language, which had a significant influence on the growth of Uzbek vocabulary at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, is intimately connected to the history of English

borrowings into Uzbek. Russian was the conduit for the initial English words into Uzbek. Numerous borrowed words with strong ties to history, geography, literature, mythology, religion, and culture may be found in both the present English and Uzbek languages. For linguistic and cultural research, as well as for one's own learning and expanding of perspectives, they are particularly interesting. Today, English is now borrowed in all facets of contemporary Uzbek. English borrowings are very prevalent in Uzbek government papers, which are crucial for learning foreign languages. Being able to pinpoint the precise moment of their assimilation into the recipient language's semantic, graphical, and grammatical structures makes official papers a useful source for linguistic analysis. According to the terms belting, upright, repetitions, nylon, cover, etc., we have categorized the words from the theme group in the fields of sociopolitical, economic, cultural-educational, and sports in the list below. -Vehicle names: tanker, pickup, liner, tanker, trolleybus, express, tram, and so on. scientific terminology -scientific disciplines, such as management and logistics economic area and trade: leasing, export, banknote, broker, voucher, dealer, discount, import, importer, investment, budget, marketing, manager, businessman, business, and many others. Undoubtedly, the conceptual picture of the language is enriched by the borrowing of new terms.

Conclusion. In conclusion, a language cannot survive without the need for a nation's culture, and a culture cannot endure without a language. It is well recognized that words may penetrate another language and affect culture. We cannot comprehend a culture first before mastering its language since they are inseparably intertwined. It is worth mentioning that hundreds of English words from many industries, such as fast food, hot dogs, bars, discos, karaoke, and others, have been incorporated into Uzbek language through cultural influences. The vocabulary of native speakers includes borrowed words because they are a part of that language's culture and background. For linguistic and cultural research, as well as for one's own learning and expanding of perspectives, they are particularly interesting.

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